

THE PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING OF COLLEGE STUDENTS ATTENDING LIMITED FACE-TO-FACE CLASSES

Shannee Rose M. Lacson, Lovelyn S. Vargas, John Lloyd L. Berdigay,
Japhet G. Enopre, Maria Dyna L. Abaño, Arlene C. Blanco
and Jose Leonardo L. Degillo, PhD, RGC, LPT, RPsy

*College of Arts and Sciences, Kabankalan Catholic College,
Kabankalan City, Philippines*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10977215>

ABSTRACT

The present study aimed to examine the psychological well-being of college students attending the limited face-to-face. This study utilized the quantitative research design. Participants of this study were 227 college students. Ryff 42-item Psychological Well-Being Scale was utilized to determine the psychological well-being of college students. According to the findings, as to the profile, male and female showed no significant percentage that they differ in psychological well-being. Regardless of sex, both had high well-being which means that both sexes reflected higher levels of overall satisfaction. As to the academic program, College of Arts and Sciences, College of Business and Accountancy, and College of Education, showed no significant percentage. This can be construed that high psychological well-being among college students were more likely to be possessed by everyone. The result of this study implies that college students of Kabankalan Catholic College have the way of having social skills, level of social responsibility, state, trait and emotional intelligence, empathy, and levels of self-concept and has high well-being and reflect higher levels of overall life satisfaction, meaning high hedonic well-being. The findings of this study suggest that students will continue to enhance their understanding of how they will positively deal with their psychological well-being and foster positive thinking.

Keywords: *academic program, limited face-to-face, pandemic, psychological well-being*

INTRODUCTION

Psychological well-being is the optimal psychological functioning and experience in life which is meant to be fully developed, individuated, matured, self-actualized and purposefully engaged in life (Ryff, 2023). It lays a solid foundation for future personality and is a crucial time in human development when life goals, values, directions, and purposes are established (Benoit & Gabola, 2021). Moreover, it consists of having positive emotions like happiness and contentment as well as the ability to develop one's potential, have some control over one's life, have a sense of purpose, and have satisfying relationships (Ruggeri et al., 2020).

Academic excellence and well-being are interconnected, encompassing social, mental, physical, and emotional well-being. It is crucial for enjoyment and life satisfaction (Mercea, 2021). The Council of Europe (2022) highlights the complexity of well-being, stating that enhancing students' wellbeing requires a culture of wellbeing across the school and active participation from all staff, which can be challenging to achieve.

The Philippines is addressing mental health issues, but lacks person-centered solutions (Malolos et al., 2021). The pandemic has increased the risk of developing mental health issues among college students, impacting academic success, social interactions, and future career opportunities (Chen & Lucock, 2022). In contrast, the pedagogical study of Gonzales et al. (2022) reiterates that there is a positive correlation between the perception of psychological well-being of participants and their academic motivation.

The above study findings and results of different authors gave us the impetus to conduct the study and to determine their psychological wellbeing and foster positive thinking. Additionally, according to the our general observations and our own experiences, the suspension of physical education classes, the disruption of daily routines, and the decline in peer social support could all have an adverse effect on the mental health of college students of Kabankalan Catholic College attending the limited face-to-face classes.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the psychological wellbeing of college students of Kabankalan Catholic College in the Academic Year 2022-2023. Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of college students when grouped according to:
 - 1.1 Sex, and
 - 1.2 Academic Program?

2. What is the level of psychological well-being of the participants as a whole and in each of the following;

- 2.1. Autonomy,
 - 2.2. Environmental Mastery,
 - 2.3. Personal Growth,
 - 2.4. Positive Relations,
 - 2.5. Purpose in Life, and
 - 2.6. Self-Acceptance?
3. Is there a significant difference in the level of psychological well-being of the participants when grouped according;
- 3.1. Sex, and
 - 3.2 Academic Program?

METHODOLOGY

This study used a quantitative research method, the process of gathering and interpreting data which is used to identify trends and averages, formulate hypotheses, examine causality, and extrapolate findings to larger populations (Bhandari, 2022). We used a descriptive research design which describes the population, circumstance, or phenomena which is intended to be correctly and methodically described through descriptive study (McCombes, 2022).

This study involved Kabankalan Catholic College students enrolled in the 2022-2023 academic year, focusing on various academic clusters. Participants were identified using systematic sampling and stratified random sampling techniques. Systematic sampling involves selecting sample members from a larger population using a fixed interval, while stratified random sampling divides a population into smaller subgroups. The study aimed to understand the impact of these methods on student outcomes. Hayes (2022) defines stratification as the division of individuals into groups based on shared traits or characteristics, such as education or income.

This study adopted the Ryff Scales of Psychological Wellbeing, an abbreviated 42-item that includes a combination of positively and negatively worded questions. It is the commonly used version of Psychological Wellbeing Scales comprises combination of positively and negatively forty-two (42) worded items. The PWB in its separate construct consists of six (6) different subscales: Autonomy, Environmental Mastery, Personal Growth, Positive Relations with Others, Purpose in Life, and Self-Acceptance subscale. The study utilized a shorter version of the PWB scale and modified six subscales, totaling 42 items, to create a more cohesive survey structure, focusing on Psychological Wellbeing as a key indicator (Celestine, 2021).

Participants were asked to rate their agreement with six subscales on Autonomy, Environmental Mastery, Personal Growth, Positive Relations, Purpose in Life, and Self-Acceptance, ranging from 1 to 7.

Since the instrument in the study used was adopted from the psychological well-

being scale of Ryff (1989), in the study of Villarosa & Ganotice (2018) it had the reliability result which was 0.82 that was conducted on Filipino Teachers, which means that the instrument was good, consistent, and measure what it is supposed to measure. In the same study, it had the internal consistencies of the subscales of PWB Scale were satisfactory: autonomy $\mu = .79$, environmental mastery $\mu = .62$, personal growth $\mu = .85$, positive relation with others $\mu = .74$, purpose in life $\mu = .78$, and self-acceptance $\mu = .66$. Other subscales used to establish the criterion related validity showed high internal consistencies: interpersonal facilitation $\mu = .90$, job dedication $\mu = .90$, and task performance $\mu = .87$.

Prior to the administration of the survey, we first asked permission from our mentor in Research in Psychology 1 subject, to the Vice President of the Academic Affairs, Dean of the College of Education, Dean of the College of Arts and Sciences, and to the Dean of College of Business and Accountancy as a gesture of courtesy.

A survey was conducted on Kabankalan Catholic College students from various academic clusters using a systematic sampling technique. The questionnaire included consent forms, demographic profiles, and the Ryff 42-item Psychological Wellbeing Scale. The scale evaluates six factors contributing to wellbeing and happiness: autonomy, environmental mastery, personal growth, meaningful relationships, purpose, and self-acceptance. The responses were retrieved, tallied, tabulated, and interpreted.

The data that were gathered in the study were subjected to the following statistical treatments.

For problem 1, frequency distribution defined as an organized tabulation or graphical representation of the number of individuals in each category on a measurement scale were used. It used frequency distribution tables in this study because frequency distribution tables are the most common type of tabulation used to indicate the frequency distribution with the aim of comparing data that has a different number of subjects (Manikandan, 2019). It indicates the observations' high and low points as well as whether they are concentrated in one place or dispersed throughout the full scale. As a result, the frequency distribution shows how the various observations are spread along the measurement scale (Young, 2022).

For problem 2, we used the mean to determine the psychological well-being of the college students attending limited face-to-face classes. A set of two or more numbers is simply averaged mathematically to get the term "mean". According to Hayes (2022), there are several ways to calculate the mean for a given collection of numbers, including as the arithmetic mean approach, which utilizes the sum of the series values, and the geometric mean method, which uses the average of a group of products. However, the majority of the time, the results from all of the main approaches to calculating a simple average are roughly the same. Moreover, the statistical mean provides crucial details about the current data set and, as a single number, can offer numerous insights on the experiment and the nature of the data (Zach, 2022).

For problem 3, to determine the significant difference in the level of psychological well-being of the participants when grouped according to sex, T-test for independent grouped was used. According to (Bevans, 2020), T-test is a test that is used to compare the means of two groups. It determines whether a process or treatment actually has an effect on the population of interest, or whether two groups are different from one another.

On the other hand, when grouped according to academic program, one-way analysis of variance was used. According to Mackenzie (2021), it is a hypothesis-based test, which means it will look at several mutually exclusive explanations about our data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1
Demographic Profile of the Participants

Profile	Frequency	Percentage
Sex		
Male	112	49.3
Female	115	50.7
Academic Program		
College of Business and Accountancy	110	48.5
College of Education	99	43.6
College of Arts and Sciences	18	7.9
Total	227	100.0

Table 1 shows the demographic profile of college students which consists of 112 males (49.3) and 115 females (50.7). Moreover, the highest number of participants were College of Business and Accountancy with 110 (48.5) participants and the lowest number were from College of Arts and Sciences with only 18 (7.9) participants.

The table reveals that female students in Kabankalan Catholic College-College Department are more likely to participate in health-related research, while males are more willing to participate in minimal risk-related studies (Otufowora et al, 2021). Moreover, 921,324 number of students were enrolled in the Philippines in business related courses making it list of top college courses (Guanzon, 2022).

Table 2.1
Level of Psychological Well-Being of the Participants in terms of Autonomy

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
I am not afraid to voice my opinions, even when they are in opposition to the opinions of most People	5.33	1.25	Very High Well-Being
My decisions are not usually influenced by what everyone else is doing	5.11	1.38	High Well-Being
I tend to be influenced by people with strong opinions.	3.13	1.54	Low Well-Being
I have confidence in my opinions, even if they are contrary to the general consensus.	4.76	1.50	High Well-Being
It's difficult for me to voice my own opinions on controversial matters.	3.15	1.58	Low Well-Being
I tend to worry about what other people think of me.	3.20	1.74	Low Well-Being
I judge myself by what I think is important, not by the values of what others think is important.	5.10	1.39	High Well-Being
Overall	4.25	0.69	Average Well-Being

Table 2.1 shows the level of Psychological Well-Being of the participants in terms of Autonomy of college students as a whole and the result was average well-being (M= 4.25, SD= 0.69), with the item number 1 on autonomy subscale, "I am not afraid to voice my opinions, even when they are in opposition to the opinions of most people" had the very high well-being, which implies that first year students persevere and persist on their opinions. Gaskell (2021) states that psychological safety in speaking up could help in promoting innovations that go against the strategies that differ from one's line or status quo. However, item number 3 on autonomy subscale (M=3.13, SD=1.54), "I tend to be influenced by people with strong opinions" has the low well-being shows that there was a presence of dominance among the environment that the first-year college was in. It is an extremely powerful phenomenon because the strong influence can dominate individuals (Schneider, 2023).

Table 2.2
Level of Psychological Well-Being of the Participants in terms of Environmental Mastery

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
In general, I feel I am in charge of the situation in which I live.	5.65	1.10	Very High Well-Being
The demands of everyday life often get me down.	3.60	1.59	Average Well-Being
I do not fit very well with the people and the community around me.	3.97	1.51	Average Well-Being
I am quite good at managing the many responsibilities of my daily life.	5.30	1.44	Very High Well-Being
I often feel overwhelmed by my responsibilities.	2.98	1.43	Low Well-Being
I have difficulty arranging my life in a way that is satisfying to me.	3.39	1.93	Average Well-Being
I have been able to build a living environment and a lifestyle for myself that is much to my liking.	5.22	1.41	High Well-Being
Overall	4.30	0.62	Average Well-Being

Table 2.2 shows the level of Psychological Well-Being of the participants in terms of environmental mastery of college students as a whole and the result was average well-being ($M= 4.30, SD=0.62$), with the item number 1 on environmental mastery subscale ($M=5.65, SD= 1.10$), “In general, I feel I am in charge of the situation in which I live.” had the very high well-being, which implies that college students of KCC are in control of their lives. Salazar and Meador (2022) stated that self-control as a mediator of learning and well-being could help for self-determination for students.

However, item number 5 on environmental mastery subscale ($M=2.98, SD=1.43$), “I often feel overwhelmed by my responsibilities” had the lowest mean and standard deviation which indicated that it had low well-being, it implies participants felt pressure in performing tasks. Moreover, oppose to the study of Ko, Shim, and Lee (2021), it states that there is willingness in college students to take tasks which is a good indicator to show the level of their social responsibility. Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems theory highlights the impact of environment on growth and development, emphasizing the importance of self-reliance in various environments throughout life (Evans, 2023).

Table 2.3
Level of Psychological Well-Being of the Participants in terms of Personal Growth

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
I am not interested in activities that will expand my horizons.	4.44	1.75	High Well-Being
I think it is important to have new experiences that challenge how you think about yourself and the world.	6.27	4.84	Extremely High Well-Being
When I think about it, I haven't really improved much as a person over the years."	3.83	1.75	Average Well-Being
I have the sense that I have developed a lot as a person over time.	5.22	1.47	High Well-Being
For me, life has been a continuous process of learning, changing, and growth.	6.63	0.90	Extremely High Well-Being
I gave up trying to make big improvements or changes in my life a long time ago.	4.03	1.95	Average Well-Being
I do not enjoy being in new situations that require me to change my old familiar ways of doing things.	4.08	1.64	Average Well-Being
Overall	4.93	0.99	High Well-Being

Table 2.3 shows the level of psychological well-being of the participants in terms of personal growth as a whole and the result was high well-being (M= 4.93, SD=0.99), with the item number 5 on personal growth subscale (M=6.63, SD= 0.90), "For me, life has been a continuous process of learning, changing, and growth" had the extremely high well-being, which revealed that participants were optimistic of how they view their life. This is supported by the study of Murphy (2023) which revealed that hope and optimism as distinct constructs influence academic performance as college students. On the other hand, Razzetti (2019) argued that optimism leads to poor outcomes, but it makes us underestimate risks or take less action.

Table 2.4
Level of Psychological Well-Being of the Participants in terms of Positive Relations

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Most people see me as loving and affectionate.	5.57	1.43	Very High Well-Being
Maintaining close relationships has been difficult and frustrating for me.	3.72	1.75	Average Well-Being
I often feel lonely because I have few close friends with whom to share my concerns.	3.96	1.84	Average Well-Being
I enjoy personal and mutual conversations with family members and friends.	5.29	1.65	High Well-Being
People would describe me as a giving person, willing to share my time with others.	5.27	1.54	High Well-Being
I have not experienced many warm and trusting relationships with others.	4.22	1.74	Average Well-Being
I know that I can trust my friends, and they know they can trust me.	5.44	1.50	Very High Well-Being
Overall	4.78	0.76	High Well-Being

Table 2.4 shows the level of psychological wellbeing of the participants in terms of positive relations as a whole and the result was high well-being (M= 4.78, SD=0.76), with the item number 1 on positive relations subscale (M=5.57, SD = 1.43), “Most people see me as loving and affectionate” had the very high well-being, which implies that participants are nurturing and passionate as other viewed them. Zhang (2022) and Siciliano (2023) highlight that passion in college students is sociologically patterned, guiding them towards quality ideological education and common value pursuit.

Table 2.5
Level of Psychological Well-Being of the Participants in terms of Purpose in Life

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
People would describe me as a giving person, willing to share my time with others.	4.89	1.73	High Well-Being
I have a sense of direction and purpose in life.	5.32	1.60	Very High Well-Being
I don't have a good sense of what it is I'm trying to accomplish in life.	4.43	1.84	Average Well-Being
My daily activities often seem trivial and unimportant to me.	4.27	1.68	Average Well-Being
I enjoy making plans for the future and working to make them a reality.	5.64	1.42	Very High Well-Being
Some people wander aimlessly through life, but I am not one of them.	4.51	1.57	High Well-Being
I sometimes feel as if I've done all there is to do in life.	4.13	1.72	Average Well-Being
Overall	4.74	0.78	High Well-Being

Table 2.5 shows the level of psychological well-being of the participants in terms of purpose in life as a whole and the result was high well-being (M= 4.74, SD=0.78), with the item number 5 on purpose in life subscale (M=5.64,SD= 1.42) , “I enjoy making plans for the future and working to make them a reality” had the very high well-being, which indicates participants vision of themselves in the future. This implies that envisioning preferred future helps someone set goals, build your strengths dream, address development needs, and map the path to success. Brimhall (2021) and Cunningham (2019) suggest that clear vision and well-planned plans lead to better goals, financial stability, and mental health, while avoiding denying present pleasures can decrease happiness over time.

Table 2.6
Level of Psychological Well-Being of the Participants in terms of Self-Acceptance

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
When I look at the story of my life, I am pleased with how things have turned out.	5.39	1.34	Very High Well-Being
In general, I feel confident and positive about myself.	5.37	1.44	Very High Well-Being
I feel like many of the people I know have gotten more out of life than I have.	4.06	1.62	Average Well-Being
I like most parts of my personality.	5.47	1.59	Very High Well-Being
In many ways I feel disappointed about my achievements in life.	3.99	1.90	Average Well-Being
My attitude about myself is probably not as positive as most people feel about themselves.	3.40	1.56	Low Well-Being
When I compare myself to friends and acquaintances, it makes me feel good about who I am.	4.78	1.62	High Well-Being
Overall	4.64	0.70	High Well-Being

Table 2.6 is the level of psychological well-being of the participants in terms of self-acceptance subscale as a whole and the result was high well-being (M= 4.64, SD=0.70).

In the self-acceptance subscale, item number 4 had the very high well-being with the mean of 5.47 and standard deviation of 1.59 which shows that participants embrace themselves. Thakadipuram (2023) stated that accepting oneself also means learning to recognize the presence of negative and positive elements and embracing it with openness. Self-acceptance requires understanding one's position, being inclusive, putting goodwill first, embracing psychological flexibility, and starting in one's sphere of influence. However, low well-being among students due to institutional and bureaucratic barriers is a significant issue (Calvez & Cummings, 2022; Fotuhi et al., 2022).

Table 2.7
Level of Psychological Well-Being of the Participants as a whole

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Autonomy	4.25	0.69	Average Well-Being
Environmental Mastery	4.30	0.62	Average Well-Being
Personal Growth	4.93	0.99	High Well-Being
Positive Relations	4.78	0.76	High Well-Being
Purpose in life	4.74	0.78	High Well-Being
Self-Acceptance	4.64	0.70	High Well-Being
Overall	4.61	0.46	High Well-Being

Table 2.7 shows the results of the level of psychological well-being of the participants as a whole with the overall result of (M=4.61, SD=0.46) which indicates high well-being and reflect higher levels of overall life satisfaction, meaning high hedonic well-being.

The study by Celestine (2021) found that participants exhibit autonomy and environmental mastery subscales, indicating self-determination, self-evaluation, competence in managing environment, controlling activities, effectively using opportunities, and choosing suitable contexts.

High well-being is characterized by positive attitudes towards self, understanding of human relationships, and a positive understanding of one's past, present, and future goals (Gao & McLellan, 2018).

Additionally, personal growth had the highest mean of 4.93 which signifies those participants believed in their own way of coping and striving for themselves. On contrary, autonomy had the lowest mean of 4.25 which means that participants had only average well-being in terms of self-determination or being independent.

Table 3
Difference Analysis on the Level of Psychological Well-Being of the Participants when grouped according to their Demographic Profile

Profile	Statistics	Level of Psychological Well-Being
Sex	Mean t-test	Male=4.60; Female=4.62
	Coefficient	-0.306
	Probability Value	0.760
	Conclusion	Not Sig.

Academic Program	Mean F-test Coefficient	CBA=4.58 COED=4.63 CAS=4.62
	Probability Value	0.310
	Conclusion	0.734
		Not Sig.

Not Sig. if p-value is greater than 0.05; sig. and highly sig. if p-value is less than 0.05 and 0.01, respectively.

Table 3 is the difference analysis on the level of psychological well-being of the participants when grouped according to their demographic profile. It reveals the profile of the participants in the locale of the study. Out of 227 participants, male has the mean of 4.60 and 4.62 for female. This means that, in the locale of the study regardless of the sex, psychological well-being between male and female are both high. Reported gender differences in mental health are shown between men and women. According to Matud, López-Curbelo, & Fortes (2019), maintaining gender norms is important for mental health and both sexes benefit from having a balanced self-concept.

Participants in various academic programs showed high psychological well-being, but varied in life satisfaction and coping strategies, indicating varying levels of overall life satisfaction.

Conclusions

The researchers conclude that male and female showed that there was no significant percentage that they differ in psychological well-being. Regardless of sex, both had high well-being which means that both sexes reflect higher levels of overall satisfaction. Also, we associated this result to the reason that differences in psychological well-being between women and men have not yielded conclusive results despite the consistently reported gender differences in mental health and respecting conventional gender norms is important for both men and women's mental health, and both sexes benefit more from having a self-concept that incorporates both masculine-instrumental and feminine- expressive traits.

As to the academic program, College of Arts and Sciences, College of Business and Accountancy, and College of Education, showed no significant percentage. This can be construed that high psychological well-being among college students were more likely to be possessed by everyone. Hence, it can be concluded that, in terms of psychological well-being dimensions, all academic program has the way of having social skills, level of social responsibility, emotional intelligence, state and trait anxiety, empathy, and levels of self-concept. However, this does not signify that these academic programs have the same way of reflecting to higher levels of overall life satisfaction. Each academic program has different way of coping and overcoming challenges in life.

In terms of the six (6) subscales of psychological well-being, all subscales

indicated high well-being and reflect higher levels of overall life satisfaction, meaning high hedonic well-being. When ranked, purpose in life has the highest mean which indicates that participants were interpreted that they have goals in life and a sense of directedness; feels there is meaning to present and past life; holds beliefs that give life purpose; has aims and objectives for living.

Recommendations

In accordance to the results of the study, its interpretations, implications, and conclusions, the following suggestions were made:

Department Heads. Department Heads must continue to provide learning opportunities to teachers such as seminars, workshops, and trainings about psychological well-being and what are the necessary measures to counterbalance psychological problems.

Teachers. They must gauge teaching strategies, styles and techniques which are responsive to learners' needs. They must also resourceful of knowing what proper remediation and intervention to take to address the issues and problems of students who has or experiencing low psychological well-being.

Counselors. They must continue to conduct series of homeroom guidance among students to correct the notion that guidance office is not a program of the school to police but to restore and transform students' behavior and concerns.

Students. They must be vocal and brave enough to share their concerns to the authorized people to help them recover and give them necessary steps to take.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Informed Consent. We gave informed consent to the participants by reading the letter for brief understanding of our study. We acted for the benefit of the respondents and supported several moral rules to put autonomy to the values and decision and by seeking the consent of the participants. The researchers have an obligation to respect the rights, needs, values, and desires of the informants (Creswell, 2018).

Data Privacy Act. We used the Data Privacy Act of 2012 and the Republic Act No. 10173 of the Philippines that measures to ensure that privacy, confidentiality, and the anonymity of the participants and their views. Bhasin (2020) stated that the ethical considerations are set of ideals and principles that should be upheld when conducting human affairs. The ethical guidelines ensure that no one acts in a way that is detrimental to society or a specific person. It forbids nasty behavior by both individuals and groups in vicious conduct.

Acknowledgements

We would like to express our heartfelt gratitude to all who served as great help, in any means, and thus made this study a success.

First and foremost, we are grateful to God Almighty for His infinite graces, guidance, and the insight He gave us to carry out this research.

Additionally, we would like to extend our sincere gratitude to Dr. Jose Leonardo L. Degillo, RGC, LPT, RPsy, who served as our adviser and contributed his knowledge and expertise to this work.

We would like to acknowledge and give special thanks to our research instructor Sheryl D. Tomo, LPT, MS, RGC, for providing invaluable notions and words, intellectual suggestions, willingness to help and assistance.

For our statistician, Paul Melcar Paglumotan, LPT, MAEd for sharing his knowledge and technical efforts during the study. For our grammarian, Marco Leo Sison, for sharing his expertise.

We would also like to thank the panel of evaluators: Rev. Fr. Eugene D. Lucerna II, PhD, RGC, RPsy; Glea Haselle A. Pabalinas, RPsM, RPsy; and Dr. Milagros Aurea A. Sabidalas, LPT for sharing their expertise in making this paper into reality.

Finally, we would like to thank our families for their unending love, support, understanding, and, most significantly, financial aid throughout the study.

REFERENCES

- Benoit, V. & Gabola, P. (2021). Effects of Positive Psychology Interventions on the Well-Being of Young Children: A Systematic Literature Review. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph182212065>
- Bevans, R. (2020). An Introduction to t Tests | Definitions, Formula and Examples. Scribbr. (n.d.). Rebecca Bevans. <https://www.scribbr.com/author/beccabevans/>
- Bhandari, P. (2022). What Is Quantitative Research? | Definition, Uses & Methods. Retrieved from; <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/quantitative-research/>
- Bhasin, H. (2020) what are ethical considerations in research? Retrieved from: <https://www.marketing91.com/ethical-considerations/>
- Brimhall, K. (2021). Envisioning your Future. Retrieved from: <https://www.jfdperfsolutions.com/envisioning-your-future/>
- Calvez, S., & Cummings, J. A. (2022). Getting on the path to indigenization: Embracing (re)conciliation in Canadian psychology. *Canadian Psychology / Psychologie Canadienne*, 63(4), 569–575. <https://doi.org/10.1037/cap0000344>

- Celestine, N. (2021). The Ryff Scales of Psychological Wellbeing: Your How-To Guide. Retrieved from; <https://positivepsychology.com/ryff-scale-psychological-wellbeing/mental-health-of-university-students-during-the-COVID-19-pandemic-An-online-survey-in-the-UK>. Retrieved from; https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_adt=0%2C5&as_ylo=2022&q=mental+health+of+college+students+in+pandemic&btnG=#d=gs_gabs&t=1673317148715&u=%23p%3DAk7x0vRTe-OJ
- Chen, T., & Lucock, M. (2022). The mental health of university students during the COVID-19 pandemic: An online survey in the UK. *PLoS ONE* 17(1): e0262562. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0262562
- Council of Europe (2022). Improving well-being at school. Retrieved from: <https://www.coe.int/en/web/campaign-free-to-speak-safe-to-learn/improving-well-being-at-school>
- Creswell, D. (2018). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and mixed methods approach 50th Edition* by John W. Creswell, J. David Creswell Paperback. Independently published.
- Cunningham, L., (2019). Envisioning your future self. Retrieved from: <https://coachingfederation.org/blog/envisioning-your-future-self>
- Fotuhi, O., Ehret, P. J., Kocsik, S., & Cohen, G. L. (2022). Boosting college prospects among low-income students: Using self-affirmation to trigger motivation and a behavioral ladder to channel it. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 122(2), 187–201. <https://doi.org/10.1037/pspa0000283>
- Gao, J., & McLellan, R. (2018). Using Ryff's scales of psychological well-being in adolescents in mainland China. *BMC Psychol.* 6:17. doi: 10.1186/s40359-018-0231-6
- Gaskell, A. (2021). Why People Don't Always Speak Up At Work. Retrieved from: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/adigaskell/2021/03/23/why-people-dont-always-speak-up-at-work/?sh=559fec6d2934>
- Gonzales, J., Lanchipa-Ale, A., Puma, E., Mansilla, E., & Laura P. (2022). Positive Dimensions of Mental Health and Personality in a Sample of University. Retrieved from; https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&as_ylo=2022&q=positive+relations+among+students+&btnG=#d=gs_qabs&t=1673404328827&u=%23p%3Dq-xIRCARQogJ
- Guanzon, A. (2022). Top 10 College Courses in the Philippines. Retrieved from: <https://www.bria.com.ph/articles/top-10-college-courses-in-the-philippines/>
- Hayes, A. (2022). Systematic Sampling is a probability, by the desired sample size. <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/s/systematic-sampling.asp#:~:text=>
- Ko, Y., Shim, SS., & Lee, H., (2021). Development and Validation of a Scale to Measure Views of Social Responsibility of Scientists and Engineers (VSRoSE). Retrieved from: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10763-021-10240-8>
- Mackenzie, R. J. (2021). One-Way vs Two-Way ANOVA: Differences, Assumptions and Hypotheses. *Informatics From Technology Networks*. <https://www.technologynetworks.com/informatics/articles/one-way-vs-two-way-anova-definition-differences-assumptions-and-hypotheses-306553>
- Malolos, G.Z.C., Baron, M.B.C., Apat, F.A.J., Sagsagat, H.A.A., Pasco, P.B.M.,

- Aportadera, E.T.C.L., Tan, R.J.D., Gacutno-Evardone, A.J., and Lucero-Prisno, III, D.E., Mental health and well-being of children in the Philippine setting during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Health Promot Perspect.* 2021 Aug 18;11(3):267-270. doi: 10.34172/hpp.2021.34. PMID: 34660220; PMCID: PMC8501475.
- Manikandan, S. (2019). Frequency distribution. *Journal of Pharmacology and Pharmacotherapeutics*, 2(1), 54–56. doi:10.4103/0976-500x.77120
- Matud, M.P., López-Curbelo, M., & Fortes, D. (2019). Gender and Psychological Well-Being. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2019 Sep 20;16(19):3531. doi: 10.3390/ijerph16193531. PMID: 31547223; PMCID: PMC6801582.
- McCombes, S. (2022). Descriptive Research | Definition, Types, Methods & Examples. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/descriptive-research/>
- Mercea, R. (2021). Why is Student Wellbeing important? Retrieved from: <https://spark.school/why-is-student-wellbeing-important/>
- Murphy, P. (2023). E-learning in teacher training: From scepticism to careful optimism. Retrieved from: https://conference.pixel-online.net/library_scheda.php?id_abs=6016
- Otufowora, A., Liu, Y., Young, H., Egan, K.L., Varma, D.S., Striley, C.W., and Cottler, L.B. (2021). Sex Differences in Willingness to Participate in Research Based on Study Risk Level Among a Community Sample of African Americans in North Central Florida. *J Immigr Minor Health.* 2021 Feb;23(1):19-25. doi: 10.1007/s10903-020-01015-4. PMID: 32328873; PMCID: PMC7714285.
- Razzetti, G. (2019). The bright and dark sides of optimism and pessimism. Retrieved from: <https://www.fearlessculture.design/blog-posts/the-bright-and-dark-sides-of-optimism-and-pessimism>
- Ryff, C.D. (2023). Flotsam, Jetsam, and Forward-Moving Vessels on the Sea of Well-Being. *Affec Sci* 4, 49–51. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42761-022-00162-1>
- Ryff, C.D. (1989) Happiness is everything, or is it? Explorations on the meaning of psychological well-being. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, <https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/full-record/WOS:A1989CJ75000014?&SID=EUW1ED0BBAJhLWO94QVR6wA7crUWC>
- Salazar, L., Meador, A., (2022). College students' grit, autonomous learning, and well-being: Self-control as a mediator. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1002/pits.22760>
- Schneider, A.M. (2023) *The Chicago School of Professional Psychology ProQuest Dissertations Publishing.* 29258351
- Siciliano, M. L. (2023). The Trouble with Passion: How Searching for Fulfillment at Work Fosters Inequality. *Contemporary Sociology*, 52(1), 31–33. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00943061221142074b>
- Thakadipuram, T. (2023). Embracing Crisis. Retrieved from: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-031-08053-1_4
- Villarosa, J., & Ganotice F. (2018). *Construct Validation of Ryff's Psychological Well-being Scale Evidence From Filipino Teachers in the Philippines* <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/326976720>
- Young, J. (2022). Frequency Distribution: Definition in Statistics and Trading. Retrieved from: <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/f/frequencydistribution.asp>

Zach, Z. (2022). Why is the Mean Important in Statistics?. Retrieved from:
<https://www.statology.org/>

Zhang, F. (2022). Proceedings of The 7th International Conference on Contemporary Education, Social Sciences and Humanities (Philosophy of Being Human as the Core of Interdisciplinary Research) (ICCESSH 2022). Retrieved from:
<https://www.atlantis-press.com/proceedings/iccessh-22/125979039>